

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO ORGAN PRESERVATION IN PURULENT-SEPTIC COMPLICATIONS IN OBSTETRICS: THE EFFICIENCY OF METROPLASTY

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Abstract. *In recent decades, the frequency of cesarean sections has significantly increased, leading to a higher risk of purulent-septic complications, including uterine suture failure and peritonitis. These conditions require urgent medical intervention, which is often associated with the risk of losing reproductive function. In recent years, organ-preserving approaches have been actively developed to maintain the reproductive capacity of women, including the use of metroplasty. Metroplasty has proven to be an effective surgical method that minimizes the volume of uterine tissue removal, which is particularly crucial for women of reproductive age.*

Keywords: *cesarean section, purulent-septic complications, uterine suture failure, peritonitis, metroplasty, organ-preserving methods.*

Uterine scar dehiscence following cesarean section represents a serious issue when planning a subsequent pregnancy. Uterine rupture at the site of the scar from a previous cesarean section occurs in 0.62–9.0% of cases and is often associated with antenatal and intranatal fetal death, as well as life-threatening hemorrhage for the pregnant woman [1, 4, 6].

Traditional methods for treating purulent-septic complications, such as hysterectomy, while effective in preventing the spread of infection, deprive women of the opportunity to have children. This is particularly critical for patients of reproductive age, for whom preserving the uterus is a vital aspect of quality of life. In this regard, the development and implementation of organ-preserving techniques, such as metroplasty, represent a promising direction in modern obstetric surgery. Metroplasty aims to eliminate the infectious focus while minimizing surgical trauma and preserving reproductive potential [10, 22].

It is believed that one of the primary causes of uterine scar dehiscence following a cesarean section is purulent-septic complications during the early postoperative period [1, 3, 5]. Purulent-septic complications in obstetrics remain one of the leading causes of maternal mortality and loss of reproductive function. The increasing frequency of cesarean sections, especially in recent decades, introduces additional risks, including uterine suture dehiscence and peritonitis. Under these circumstances, the implementation of modern diagnostic and treatment methods becomes critically important for improving the quality of medical care [20].

Timely diagnosis and treatment of these conditions are crucial. Modern methods, such as bacteriological analysis of peritoneal contents, allow for the identification of infectious agents and

the selection of effective antibiotics [16, 19]. The primary microorganisms responsible for purulent-septic processes include gram-negative bacteria (e.g., *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella*) and gram-positive organisms (e.g., *Staphylococci*, *Streptococci*) [7].

Previously, hysterectomy was the main treatment method for severe infections associated with cesarean sections, which deprived women of the ability to have children [1, 8]. The development of organ-preserving treatment methods, such as metroplasty, has opened new possibilities [4]. This technique allows for the restoration of uterine integrity even in complex cases [3, 8].

The relevance of the topic is also driven by the need to improve the quality of medical care for women with purulent-septic complications, especially in settings with limited resources and a high workload on medical facilities. Modern innovative approaches, based on the use of metroplasty, not only help reduce maternal mortality but also improve reproductive and overall clinical outcomes, emphasizing the importance of further research and implementation in clinical practice.

Given the potential complications associated with an inadequate uterine scar following cesarean section (CS), the aim of this study was to review the literature and evaluate the effectiveness of the organ-preserving surgery metroplasty in treating obstetric peritonitis caused by uterine suture dehiscence after cesarean section.

Any surgical intervention, including cesarean section, carries risks of various complications, with inflammatory processes being among the most prevalent. Despite advancements in surgical techniques, the use of modern suture materials, and the administration of antibacterial drugs, cesarean section remains a complex procedure that poses an additional risk of postpartum postoperative complications [2, 12].

The risk of developing purulent-inflammatory diseases after cesarean section is 20 times higher than after vaginal delivery [7, 9]. It is well known that an increase in the cesarean section rate by 1% doubles the incidence of postpartum purulent-septic complications. Maternal mortality following cesarean section, especially repeat procedures, is four times higher than after vaginal delivery [1, 7]. There are numerous causes of uterine scar insufficiency after cesarean section, including intraoperative bleeding, injury to adjacent organs, improper surgical technique, and postoperative complications [9, 10].

One of the most severe purulent-septic complications, accompanied by high mortality rates (15–40%), is obstetric peritonitis [11]. In 98% of cases, obstetric peritonitis results from complications of cesarean section, while in 1–2% of cases, it is caused by an exacerbation of inflammatory processes in the uterine appendages. Peritoneal infection leading to obstetric peritonitis after cesarean section occurs via three pathways: in 30% of cases, infected uterine cavity contents enter the peritoneal cavity during surgery; in 15%, intestinal microflora penetrates the peritoneal cavity due to postoperative intestinal paresis; and in 55%, peritoneal infection arises from uterine suture dehiscence against the background of endometritis [11, 14].

Uterine suture dehiscence, in turn, is associated with improper suture application in 70% of cases, inadequate hemostasis during surgery with subsequent hematoma formation at the surgical site, which becomes infected. In 30% of cases, it is due to the patient's impaired reparative abilities [12, 16, 17].

According to international statistics, the incidence of severe sepsis with fatal outcomes is increasing by 10% annually. The main risk factors include advanced maternal age, obesity,

pregnancy complicated by chronic diseases, multiple pregnancies, and the high rate of cesarean sections (risk increased by 5–20 times) [5, 13].

The rapid progression of the septic process may be due to a decrease in the activity of the cellular immune component and the maternal systemic inflammatory response, which is manifested by changes in the Th1/Th2 ratio, increased susceptibility to intracellular pathogens (bacteria, viruses, parasites), increased leukocyte count, elevated D-dimer levels, endothelial dysfunction, reduced levels of protein S and fibrinolytic activity, an increase in the level of pro-inflammatory cytokines during labor, and the presence of an inflammatory response in pregnancy complications (preeclampsia, eclampsia, premature labor) [2,11,22].

Among the factors influencing the increase in the number of surgeries are the development of diagnostic technologies, such as cardiotocography and ultrasound, as well as demographic changes. These include the increasing age of first-time mothers and the rise in cases of pregnancy resulting from in vitro fertilization [14,18]. Despite the positive impact on fetal health, surgical intervention is associated with an increased risk of complications for women, including infectious diseases [6,21].

Early diagnosis and treatment of complications are critical. The use of modern methods, such as abdominal cavity content analysis, helps identify pathogens and administer appropriate therapy [15]. Among the microbes that cause infections, gram-negative bacteria, such as *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella*, as well as gram-positive bacteria, including staphylococci and streptococci, are most commonly encountered [20].

Despite advances in treatment, problems remain, such as the timely detection of complications, access to qualified medical care, and adherence to therapy standards [14]. Additionally, research into the long-term outcomes in patients who have undergone such treatment is required [1,9].

Research confirms that timely application of metroplasty reduces the risk of infection spread, improves treatment outcomes, and contributes to the preservation of reproductive function [3, 4, 16]. The use of modern suturing materials and effective antibiotic therapy also decreases the likelihood of recurrences [7, 18].

Despite advances in the treatment of purulent-septic complications, challenges remain, such as the need for early detection of issues, access to qualified medical care, and adherence to therapy standards [14]. It is also important to study the long-term outcomes in women who have undergone organ-preserving surgeries [1, 9].

Thus, the relevance of developing and implementing new methods for treating infectious complications is supported by numerous data. Metroplasty has proven to be an effective approach for preserving the health and reproductive capabilities of women with severe complications [8,18]. The application of this method in practice helps improve the quality of life for patients [13,17].

The data confirms the need for the introduction of modern methods of treating infectious complications. Metroplasty has established itself as an effective method capable of preserving reproductive function in women with severe complications [8,18]. The use of this approach in clinical practice contributes to improving the quality of life for patients [7,19].

Conclusion. The results of researchers confirm the importance of metroplasty in modern obstetrics and emphasize the need for further development of organ-preserving technologies to improve treatment outcomes and the quality of life of patients. The application of innovative organ-preserving methods, such as metroplasty, in the treatment of purulent-septic complications

in obstetrics demonstrates high clinical effectiveness. Metroplasty reduces the risk of reproductive function loss, minimizes blood loss, shortens rehabilitation periods, and reduces the recurrence of infectious complications. These results highlight the need for further implementation and dissemination of this method in obstetric practice, which is especially relevant for women of reproductive age. Further research in this area should focus on improving the surgical technique and developing standards for the application of metroplasty in various clinical situations.

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